

SEMICONDUCTOR MATERIALS

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Annatations. Of the 104 elements of the periodic table, 79 are metals, 25 are non-metals, 13 of them have chemical elements, and 12 are dielectrics. The main difference between semiconductors is that their electrical conductivity increases significantly with increasing temperature. At low temperatures they act like dielectrics and at high temperatures they act like conductors. These semiconductors differ from metal: the resistance of the metal increases in proportion to the increase in temperature.

Keywords. Semiconductors, dielectrics, systems, LED, n-type, p-type.

Semiconductors These are elements that selectively perform the function of conductors or insulators depending on external conditions such as temperature, pressure, radiation, and magnetic or electric fields [1-5].

If they are used as conductors, under certain conditions they allow the flow of electricity, but only in one direction. They are also not as highly conductive as conductive metals.

Semiconductors are used in electronic applications, especially to manufacture components such as transistors, diodes, and integrated circuits. They are also used as supplements or additions to optical sensors such as solid-state lasers and some power supplies for power transmission systems [6-8].

Figure 1.1 (connection of silicon semiconductor)

Currently, this type of element is used in both domestic and industrial applications for technological developments in the fields of telecommunications, control systems and signal processing.

There are 14 semiconductor elements in the periodic table, including silicon, germanium, selenium, cadmium, aluminum, gallium, boron, indium, and carbon. Semiconductors are crystalline solids with moderate electrical conductivity, so they can be used dually as conductors and insulators [9-10].

Semiconductors are substances that occupy an intermediate position between substances that conduct electricity well (conductors, mainly metals) and substances that do not conduct electricity (dielectrics). Most of the elements in Mendeleev's periodic table are in groups II, III, IV, V and VI. A number of their compounds are included in semiconductors. In semiconductors, as in metals, electrical conductivity occurs due to the movement of electrons. However, the conditions of movement of electrons are different in metals and semiconductors [11-13]. Semiconductors have the following main properties: The electrical conductivity of semiconductors increases with temperature increase (for example, when the temperature increases by 1 K, the specific conductivity of semiconductors increases 16-17 times); In addition to free electrons, electrons bound to atoms also participate in the electrical conductivity of semiconductors (in some cases, bound electrons play a key role); by adding a small amount of dopant to pure semiconductors, its conductivity can be dramatically changed (for

example, when adding 0.01% dopant, the conductivity of semiconductors increases 10,000 times). At low temperatures, the specific resistance of semiconductors is very large and in practice they are considered insulators, but with an increase in temperature, the concentration of charge carriers in them increases sharply [14-15]. For example, if the concentration of free electrons in pure silicon is $\sim 10^{17} \text{ m}^{-3}$ at a temperature of 20° . At 700° , it increases to 10^{24} m^{-3} , that is, more than a million times. Such a sharp dependence of the concentration of free electrons on the band in semiconductors indicates that conduction electrons are formed under the influence of thermal motion. In a semiconductor crystal, atoms are interconnected using valence electrons. During thermal vibrations of atoms, thermal energy is unevenly distributed among valence electrons [16-18].

	III	IV	V	VI	VII
1					
2	B	C	N	O	F
3	Al	Si	P	S	Cl
4	Ga	Ge	As	Se	Br
5	In	Sn	Sb	Te	I
6	Tl	Pb	Bi	Po	At

Half There are 2 types of conductors is divided _

1- internal semiconductors _ _

2- external semiconductor conductors

If the material is an intrinsic semiconductor, it is able to transmit electricity in its pure state, that is, without impurities and other atoms.

External semiconductors. They differ from intrinsic semiconductors because they contain small amounts of impurities (trivalent or pentavalent elements) [19-20]. A certain change can be made to the molecular structure of the silicon or germanium crystal to allow electric current to flow in only one direction. The

process of applying impurities is called "doping".

N semiconductor. To increase the amount of free electrons, a doping substance is added that allows the transfer of electric charge. At the same time, the N-type semiconductor is not a good conductor, as is the case of the electrical conductor.

Semiconductor type P. Instead of adding a doping material that increases the number of electrons, trivalent atoms or compounds are added to the material, which when added to the semiconductor atoms create holes (electron deficiency). Thus, the material becomes conductive with a positive charge [21-22].

In order to make a semiconductor more conductive, in addition to doping, its temperature can be increased.

N -junction materials made it possible to create devices that replaced electronic tubes, revolutionizing telecommunications due to their small size, reduced energy consumption, and lower cost. Semiconductor materials there is was the most important program this diodes . This electricity elements is variable vine right - right to the flow rotate to the function have , this rectification that is called Diodes are also used in solar panels that convert solar energy into electricity and as LED lights [23-24].

Semiconductors with high purity of inputs are not very low at temperatures, its specific charge under the influence of an external electric field carriers - electricity due to the directed movement of electrons and holes will have conductivity. This electrical conductivity of semiconductors is called specific conductivity.

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